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Effect of Moisture Saturation on Thermal Expansion Coefficients of Composites

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Factors effecting dimensional stability

- During cure resin shrinkage causes a residual tensile stress within a composite (e.g. springback)
- Once produced the dimensional stability is governed by environmental factors, primarily change in temperature and moisture content

Hubble Telescope
Metering Truss Structure

Propeller Shaft
Composite Bearing

Composite materials studied

A range of unidirectional carbon and glass fabrics were chosen and vacuum resin infused with the same epoxy resin (Kinetix R118-H103)

Fibre Type	Carbon			E-Glass	
Areal Weight (gm ⁻²)	300	450	500	250	500
Tow Size	12000	24000	50000	3000	6000

Thermomechanical analysis (TMA) samples

Composite blocks nominally 15mm x 15mm x 5mm

Variable factors

- Fibre type
- Number of plies
- Ply thickness
- Tow size

Sample Name	Average Block Thickness (mm)	Number of plies in laminate	Average Block Ply Thickness (mm)
C-300	5.27	20	0.264
C-450	5.65	12	0.471
C-500	5.32	10	0.532
E-250	5.67	30	0.189
E-500	6.80	20	0.340

Thermal expansion measurement

- Thermal expansion was measured using NETZSCH TMA 402 thermomechanical analyser
- Dry block samples were measured in all 3 orientations (x,y,z), moisture saturated in 2 orientations (y and z)
- Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE, α) obtained using slope of line

Sample mounted in TMA
 $1 \text{ microstrain}^\circ\text{C} = 1 \text{ ppm}^\circ\text{C}$

TMA result for E250 in transverse direction (y)

Measured CTE for dry composites

Sample	Transverse CTE, α_y (microstrain/°C)	Through-thickness CTE, α_z (microstrain/°C)	Longitudinal CTE, α_x (microstrain/°C)	Fiber Volume (%)
C300	43.6	51.2	-0.4	55
C450	44.9	47.9	-0.6	53
C500	47.8	53.6	-0.5	51
E250	37.9	46.0	7.3	55
E500	32.2	39.2	6.3	57

neat epoxy resin CTE = 64.3 microstrain/°C

T700 carbon fibre longitudinal CTE = -0.38 microstrain/°C

E Glass fibre longitudinal CTE = 5.4 microstrain/°C

Schapery's expressions

$$\alpha_x = \frac{E_f \alpha_f V_f + E_m \alpha_m V_m}{E_f V_f + E_m V_m}$$

Approx. 1.0 for carbon and 9.5 for glass

$$\alpha_y = (1 + \nu_f) \alpha_f V_f + (1 + \nu_m \alpha_m V_m - \alpha_x (\nu_f V_f + \nu_m V_m))$$

Approx. 31 for carbon and 33 for glass

Change in neat resin CTE with moisture saturation

Non-Fickian moisture uptake in epoxy resin so CTE measured at 2.75% moisture content

Glass transition temperature also reduced by 11°C

Change in composites CTE with moisture saturation

Through thickness CTE

50% increase for carbon fibre composites

75% increase for glass fibre composites

Transverse CTE

20% - 50% increase for composites

No clear correlations but less than through thickness

Moisture Expansion

Moisture expansion also measured on the samples

Coefficient of Moisture Expansion, β obtained from slope of line

$$CME = \beta = \frac{\Delta L}{L_0} \div \frac{\Delta m}{m_0} \%$$

Through thickness CME nearly twice that of transverse CME for all samples

Sample	Transverse CME, β_y (millistrain/%M)	Through-thickness CME, β_z (millistrain/%M)
C300	3.7	6.2
C450	3.4	6.4
C500	3.6	5.4
E250	3.4	6.7
E500	3.2	5.0

1 millistrain/%M = 1000 ppm/%M = 0.1% strain/%M

Neat epoxy resin CME, $\beta_m = 2.41$ millistrain/ $^{\circ}$ C

Schapery's expression $\beta_y = \beta_m V_m (1 + v_m)$

Approx. 1.5 for carbon and 1.4 for glass

Moisture absorption of E500 block

Dimensional change vs moisture content C450 block

Summary of results

- After moisture saturation resin CTE increases by 75% and this is reflected in significant increases in CTEs for moisture saturated composites
- While dry through thickness CTEs were 10-20% higher than the transverse CTEs, after moisture saturation through thickness CTEs are 25-65% higher than the transverse CTEs
- When expansion due to the moisture uptake is also considered very high internal strains result even with relatively small changes in temperature

Conclusions

- While it is usually assumed that for unidirectional composites that transverse and through thickness expansions will be very similar, the experimental results show that this clearly not the case
- The changes in thermal expansion behaviour with uptake of moisture is significant and cannot be ignored due to the higher internal strains that result from modest changes in temperature

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